

A COMPACT SPS-BASED PARALLEL MECHANISM FOR WORM-LIKE ROBOT LOCOMOTION IN CONFINED ENVIRONMENTS

Angelos Iliakis¹, George Nikolakopoulos¹, Panagiotis Koustoumpardis¹

¹ University of Patras, Department of Mechanical Engineering and Aeronautics, Greece, {a.iliakis,gnikolak,koust}@upatras.gr

1 ABSTRACT

Locomotion and steering of worm- and snake-like robots in confined environments are particularly challenging when high axial forces must be transmitted through compact mechanical structures. Most existing approaches rely on serial bending joints or wave-based gaits, which typically exhibit limited stiffness and reduced force transmission under constrained conditions. This work presents a compact parallel mechanism based on a combination of Spherical-Prismatic-Spherical (SPS) joints, designed as the core kinematic unit of a modular worm-like robot for confined and tubular environments. The mechanism enables controlled axial motion and local orientation adjustment using three coordinated linear actuators, while inherently distributing external loads across multiple parallel load paths. A concise forward and inverse kinematic formulation is derived, and the attainable workspace is analyzed under geometric constraints imposed by a cylindrical robotic module.

2 INTRODUCTION

Robotic locomotion in confined and tubular environments is critical for subsurface exploration and drilling. Most worm- and snake-like robots rely on serial bending joints or wave-based strategies, which suffer from limited stiffness and reduced force transmission under high axial loads. In thrust-driven confined systems, steering must coexist with significant load transfer within compact cylindrical envelopes. Also steering and load transmission must be structurally coupled. Parallel kinematic mechanisms inherently distribute loads across multiple chains, yet their integration into worm-like architectures remains a challenging research problem [1], [2], [3].

3 MECHANISM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed mechanism follows a Spherical-Prismatic-Spherical (SPS) parallel configuration composed of three identical linear actuators symmetrically arranged around the central axis.

Figure 1: Assembly of the robotic system with the SPS module integrated: (a) SPS joint configuration, (b) CAD model, and (c) SPS actuation angles within the robot.

Each leg connects the base and the moving platform through a spherical joint at the base, an actuated prismatic joint, and a spherical joint at the platform. The mechanism is integrated within a cylindrical robotic module, imposing strict geometric constraints. Coordinated actuation enables axial translation and controlled tilting about two orthogonal axes while distributing external loads across parallel chains.

4 KINEMATICS

The SPS mechanism is modeled as a three-degree-of-freedom parallel system. The generalized coordinate vector is defined as

$$\mathbf{q} = [\alpha \quad \beta \quad h]^T, \quad (1)$$

where α and β denote the platform tilting angles about the base x - and y -axes, respectively, and h represents the translation along the local platform axis.

The platform orientation is expressed by the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}(\alpha, \beta)$. Let the head (tool tip) be located at a fixed offset L_h along the local platform axis. Its position in the global frame is given by

$$\mathbf{p}_h = \mathbf{p}_0 + (h + L_h) \mathbf{R}(\alpha, \beta) \hat{\mathbf{z}}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{z}} = [0 \quad 0 \quad 1]^T, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{p}_0 is a fixed reference point on the base.

The attainable head workspace is then defined as

$$\mathcal{W}_h = \{ \mathbf{p}_h \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid h_{\min} \leq h \leq h_{\max}, |\alpha| \leq \alpha_{\max}, |\beta| \leq \beta_{\max} \}. \quad (3)$$

Figure 2: Workspace of the SPS mechanism: (a) head workspace visualization and (b) full reachable workspace of the mechanism.

The inverse kinematic problem consists of determining the required actuator elongations for a desired platform pose. The desired position of the platform reference point is computed through Eqs.(1-2) and substituting the desired pose into the forward kinematic relations yields the actuator commands

$$l_{i,d} = \|\mathbf{p}_d + \mathbf{R}(\alpha_d, \beta_d) \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{b}_i\|, \quad i = 1, 2, 3. \quad (4)$$

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a compact SPS-based parallel mechanism and its concise kinematic formulation for worm-like robot locomotion in confined environments. By distributing axial loads across parallel kinematic chains, the proposed joint mechanism architecture enhances force transmission compared to conventional serial designs. The derived forward and inverse kinematics establish a well-conditioned and compact workspace suitable for sensor-driven steering and thrust generation.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the European Horizon Project Minotaur Grant No.101178775

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Cammarata, P. D. Maddio, R. Sinatra, Y. Tian, Y. Zhao, and F. Xi, “Elastostatic analysis of a module-based shape morphing snake-like robot,” *Mechanism and Machine Theory*, vol. 194, p. 105580, 2024.
- [2] L. Douadi, D. Spinello, W. Gueaieb, and H. Sarfraz, “Planar kinematics analysis of a snake-like robot,” *Robotica*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 659–675, 2013.
- [3] I. Virgala, M. Kelemen, P. Bozek, Z. Bobovsky, and M. Hagara, “Investigation of snake robot locomotion possibilities in a pipe,” *Symmetry*, vol. 12, no. 6, p. 939, 2020.